

Individual Paper Proposal #1

The Anime OP(ening): a Corpus Study of Anison

This paper presents a corpus study comprising 348 anime opening credits (OPs) released between 1989–2024, to highlight formal and audiovisual conventions. The OP serves many functions in relation to the series, including: introducing the title and protagonists, genre, themes/plot, and production credits, all of which grab the attention of viewers before the start of the episode-proper.

This study builds on corpus studies of pop music in two aspects. First, it complements broader corpora on contemporary J-pop—such as Ramage’s (2023) research on the Royal Road progression—by focusing on how the subgenre of *anison* interacts with a television program’s formal/temporal constraints. Second, it extends Nazare’s (2023) research on anison’s form archetypes and expands their “historico-hermeneutic” approach (Martin 2024).

The author gathered data on 200 OPs from the top 200 anime on *MyAnimeList.net*, and on 148 OPs from the *Japan Billboard Hot Animation* year-end charts, 2013–24. The corpus encodes information regarding an OP’s associated anime (title, year, demographics), musical form (formal units, form archetype), vocals (singer’s sex, rapped/sung, language), and visual devices (title screen, protagonists/antagonists, cinematography); see Figure 1. In doing so, this study enables an in-depth look on how formal characteristics work in tandem with visual images to capture viewers’ attention.

The first significant finding concerns trends in OP’s form, or the “OP format.” With very few exceptions, OPs are adapted from a full-length musical track averaging 2–4 minutes. This adaptation typically results in an abridged verse–chorus form: a “call” (described below), a verse, a prechorus, a chorus, and an outro (usually a postchorus adaptation). Figure 2 summarizes three deviations from the standard OP format.

The second finding surrounds a common formal unit positioned at the start of the OP which functions as an attention grabber, or the “call.” The majority of the OPs in this corpus (77.1%) feature a call. For example, consider the OP “again” by YUI for the anime *Hagane no Renkinjutsushi* (2009). As Figure 3 shows, the call anticipates an equally texturally dense chorus. The call starts with the vocals singing the chorus lyrics in the foreground, and later develops into a full band chorus instrumental, where the series’ title appears on screen. This two-phrase call acts as an attention grabber and an anticipatory section (in this case, anticipating the chorus). The call is differentiated from similar formal units such as “overture choruses” (Nobile 2020), “chorus-first forms” (Ensign 2015), “core-based intros” (Summach 2012), and “buildup introductions” (Attas 2015) in two aspects: calls are texturally busy and often timbrally bright (Malawey 2020), and anticipate a musical climax, usually the chorus or postchorus.

These characteristics are not Japan-specific: this study motivates research in cartoon music trends in the West, too. For example, the tritone chorus in *The Simpsons* or the shout “Yabba Dabba Doo” in *The Flintstones* both fit the description of a call section. This study shows that both the OP format and call are part of a thought-through framework to entice the viewer, motivating them to watch the anime about to start.

Selected Bibliography and Examples

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